

Figured Magic Squares of Order 34 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure

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Abstract

*Recently, the author constructed even order magic squares from orders 6 to 30 with different styles and models, for examples the order 20 is with 1616 magic squares, order 18 with 810 magic squares, etc. These can be seen at [31, 32, 33, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37]. The aim is to proceed for the further orders of magic squares. A systematic procedure to construct these magic squares is given. It is based on the magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 etc. at **corners** and small blocks of **bordered magic rectangles** forming external borders. Then the internal borders are filled with previous known magic squares. The presentation is in figures instead of numbers. The readers can find replies in numbers from references given above. For the orders multiples of 4, we can always write magic squares with equal sums of blocks of magic squares of order 4. This procedure is very helpful for the orders of type $2p$, where p is a prime number, for example, 14, 22, 26, 34, 38, etc. For the orders like 18, 30, 42, etc. we can make good external blocks with order 4, and for orders like 16, 20, 28, 32, etc. we can make good external borders of order 6, and so on. Based on this idea the author wrote even order magic squares up to order 32. For details refer [38, 39, 40, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47]. This work is for the magic squares of order 34 represented in terms of figures.*

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1 Introduction

The magic sums of order n of consecutive numbers from 1 to n^2 is given by

$$S_{n \times n} := \frac{n \times (1 + n^2)}{2}, n \geq 3. \quad (1)$$

Recently, the author [31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37] constructed magic squares of even orders from 8 to 20 using **bordered magic rectangles**. This construction is based on two aspects:

- (i) Using **magic rectangles** or **bordered magic rectangles**.
- (ii) Using algebraic formula like $(\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b})^2, \mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{b}$.

For the above magic squares no construction procedure is explained. The aim is to proceed further orders of magic squares. In this work, a systematic procedure to construct these magic squares is given. It is based on the magic squares and bordered magic rectangles (BMR) of orders 4, 6, 8 etc forming external borders. Then the internal borders are filled with previous known magic squares. For the orders multiples of 4, we can always write magic squares with equal sums blocks of magic squares of order 4. This procedure is very helpful for the orders of type $2\mathbf{p}$, where \mathbf{p} is a prime number, for examples, 14, 22, 26, 34, 38, etc. For the orders like 18, 30, etc., we can make good external blocks with order 4, and for orders like 16, 20, 28, 32, etc. we can make good external borders of order 6, and so on. There is no explanations for the orders 6, 8, 10 and 12. The real construction starts from the order 14.

The whole the work is done manually, without use of any programming language, except for the constructions of small blocks of **bordered magic rectangles**. This construction is based on the software due to H. While [1]. Later, these BRMs are readopted according to distribution of each magic square. The distribution of **magic squares** or **bordered magic rectangles** is based on **half-sequential** numbers. By **half-sequential** numbers we understand that the total numbers in each case are divided in two equal parts. The first part is one sequence and the second part is another sequence. Due to **half-sequential** numbers, it is not possible to construct all orders **bordered magic rectangles**. In Appendix 3, there are tables showing the existence of these **bordered magic rectangles** for **half-sequential**. For simplicity, we shall write **BMR** as **bordered magic rectangle**. This work is for order 34. The previous works can be seen at [38, 39, 40, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47].

Remark 1. *The bordered magic squares and bordered magic rectangles are with the property that if we remove external borders in each case, still we are left with bordered magic squares and bordered magic rectangles respectively with sequential number entries. The whole work is in figures instead of numbers. In the same magic square the small equal figures represents equal sums magic squares and/or equal sums bordered magic rectangles.*

2 Magic Squares of Order 34

This section brings in figures (without numbers) magic squares of order 34. In some cases, the idea of constructions are explained. It is based on **cornered magic squares**.

2.1 Cornered Magic Squares of Order 4

Let's consider an external border, where there are 4 magic squares of order 4 at the corners. Let's make an external border by putting 4 BMRs of orders 4×26 in each row and column. We are left with inner block of order 26. Writing these inner blocks with different types of magic squares of order 26, we get magic squares of order 34. See below few examples:

2.2 Closed Border of Order 4

The external border is made with 4 BMRs of order 4×30 . We are left with inner block of order 26. Writing these inner blocks with different types of magic squares of order 26, we get magic squares of order 34. See below few examples:

2.3 Cornered Magic Squares of Order 6

Let's consider an external border, where there are 8 magic squares of order 6 and 4 BMRs of order 6×16 . This gives us an external border with cornered magic squares of order 6. In the middle we are left with block of order 22. Writing this inner blocks with different types of magic squares of order 20, we get magic squares of order 34. See below few examples:

2.4 Closed Border of Order 6

The external border is made with 6 BMRs of order 6×28 . We are left with inner block of order 22. Writing these inner blocks with different types of magic squares of order 22, we get magic squares of order 34. See below few examples:

2.5 Cornered Magic Squares of Order 8

Let's consider an external border, where there are 4 magic squares of order 8 at corners and in the middle there 4 BMRs of order 8×18 . This gives us an external border with cornered magic squares of order 8. We are left with inner block of order 18. Writing these inner blocks with different types of magic squares of order 18, we get magic squares of order 34. See below few examples:

2.6 Closed Border of Order 8

The external border is made with 4 BMRs of order 8×26 . We are left with inner block of order 18. Writing these inner blocks with different types of magic squares of order 18, we get magic squares of order 34. See below few examples:

2.7 Cornered Magic Squares of Order 10

Let's consider an external border, where there are 4 magic squares of order 10 at corners and in the middle there 4 magic squares of order 10 and 4 BMRs of order 4×10 . This gives us an external border with cornered magic squares of order 10. We are left with inner blocks of order 14. Writing these inner blocks with different types of magic squares of order 14, we get magic squares of order 34. See below few examples:

Remark 2. *In the above case, the middle part is not symmetric. We can make it symmetric by considering 2 BMRs of Order 4×10 , one magic square of order 10 and one 4×6 . It is left for the reader to check it.*

2.8 Closed Border of Order 10

The external border is made with 4 BMRs of order 10×24 . We are left with inner block of order 14. Writing these inner blocks with different types of magic squares of order 14, we get magic squares of order 34. See below few examples:

2.9 Cornered Magic Squares of Order 12

Let's consider an external border, where there are 4 magic squares of order 12 at corners and in the middle there 4 BMRs of order 10×12 . This gives us an external border with cornered magic squares of order 12. We are left with inner block of order 10. Writing these inner blocks with different types of magic squares of order 10, we get magic squares of order 34. See below few examples:

2.10 Closed Border of Order 12

The external border is made with 4 BMRs of order 12×22 . We are left with inner block of order 10. Writing these inner blocks with different types of magic squares of order 10, we get magic squares of order 34. See below few examples:

2.11 Cornered Magic Squares of Order 14

Let's consider an external border, where there are 4 magic squares of order 14 at corners and in the middle there 4 magic squares of order 6 and 4 BMRs of order 6×8 . This gives us an external border with cornered magic squares of order 14. We are left with inner block of order 6. Making different choices of order 14, we get magic squares of order 34. See below few examples:

2.12 Closed Border of Order 14

The external border is made with 4 BMRs of order 10×22 . We are left with inner block of order 6. This gives us following magic squares of order 34:

2.13 BMRs of Orders 16×18 , and Magic Squares Orders 16 and 18

3 Appendix

Below are tables giving the existence of **bordered magic rectangles** for **half-sequential** numbers.

Order of Magic Square	Bordered Magic Rectangles
6	4×6
8	6×8
10	$4 \times 10, 8 \times 10$
12	$6 \times 12, 10 \times 12$
14	$4 \times 14, 8 \times 14, 12 \times 14$
16	$6 \times 16, 10 \times 16, 14 \times 16$
18	$4 \times 18, 8 \times 18, 12 \times 18$
20	$6 \times 20, 10 \times 20, 14 \times 20, 18 \times 20$
22	$4 \times 22, 8 \times 22, 12 \times 22,$ $16 \times 22, 20 \times 22$
24	$6 \times 24, 10 \times 24, 14 \times 24,$ $18 \times 24, 22 \times 24$
26	$4 \times 26, 8 \times 26, 12 \times 26,$ $16 \times 26, 20 \times 26, 24 \times 26$
28	$6 \times 28, 10 \times 28, 14 \times 28,$ $18 \times 28, 22 \times 28, 26 \times 28$
30	$4 \times 30, 8 \times 30, 12 \times 30, 16 \times 30,$ $20 \times 30, 24 \times 30, 28 \times 30$
32	$6 \times 32, 10 \times 32, 14 \times 32, 18 \times 32,$ $22 \times 32, 26 \times 32, 30 \times 32$
34	$4 \times 34, 8 \times 34, 12 \times 34, 16 \times 34,$ $20 \times 34, 24 \times 34, 28 \times 34, 32 \times 34$

Order of Magic Square	Bordered Magic Rectangles
36	$6 \times 36, 10 \times 36, 14 \times 36, 18 \times 36, 22 \times 36, 26 \times 36, 30 \times 36, 34 \times 36$
38	$4 \times 38, 8 \times 38, 12 \times 38, 16 \times 38, 20 \times 38, 24 \times 38, 28 \times 38, 32 \times 38, 36 \times 38$
40	$6 \times 40, 10 \times 40, 14 \times 40, 18 \times 40, 22 \times 40, 26 \times 40, 30 \times 40, 34 \times 40, 38 \times 40$
42	$4 \times 42, 8 \times 42, 12 \times 42, 16 \times 42, 20 \times 42, 24 \times 42, 28 \times 42, 32 \times 42, 36 \times 42, 40 \times 42$
44	$6 \times 44, 10 \times 44, 14 \times 44, 18 \times 44, 22 \times 44, 26 \times 44, 30 \times 44, 34 \times 44, 38 \times 44, 42 \times 44$
46	$4 \times 46, 8 \times 46, 12 \times 46, 16 \times 46, 20 \times 46, 24 \times 46, 28 \times 46, 32 \times 46, 36 \times 46, 40 \times 46, 44 \times 46$
48	$6 \times 48, 10 \times 48, 14 \times 48, 18 \times 48, 22 \times 48, 26 \times 48, 30 \times 48, 34 \times 48, 38 \times 48, 42 \times 48, 46 \times 48$
50	$4 \times 50, 8 \times 50, 12 \times 50, 16 \times 50, 20 \times 50, 24 \times 50, 28 \times 50, 32 \times 50, 36 \times 50, 40 \times 50, 44 \times 50, 48 \times 50$

4 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation numbers** please see the links below:

- Inder J. Taneja, Magic Squares, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- Inder J. Taneja, Recreation of Numbers, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

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